

Comparing ground-based and satellite retrievals of cloud fraction over the Amazon

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Abstract

In this research, we've done an exploratory analysis on Sky Cloud Cover Fraction variables retrieved from 2014 to 2015 in Manacapuru/AM - Brazil from several instruments - GOES-13 and MODIS Aqua/Terra satellites, and ground-based platforms from the GOAmazon project: the Total Sky Imager and the Radiative Flux Analyzer using Long et al. and Xie & Liu et al. algorithms - with the objective of characterize the influence of annual season, the choice of spatio-temporal windows and the solar geometry on the comparability between the different instruments. Using Pearson's correlation coefficient as a comparison metric, we've found that different choices of spatio-temporal window applied to a daily basis have an significant impact on the comparability between the platforms and that the ideal choices changes along the day. Also, we've found that the annual season have an impact on the comparability between the instruments. We've compiled a commented table containing a synthesis of the ideal choices of spatio-temporal windows which will maximize the comparability between the studied platforms.

1. Introduction

One of the greatest challenges when acquiring Sky Cloud Cover values, which is a measure of the fraction of sky covered by clouds, consists on the definition of the word “cloud” (Kassianov et al., 2005; Wu et al. 2014). To quantify how much a given area is covered by clouds, the retrieval procedure must take into account the observer characteristics, the observation geometry, the adopted measurement system for detection, and even the methodology for analyzing the measurements. The use of different algorithms and spectral bands for cloud detection can produce cloud fraction estimates that are markedly different. For example, when it is considered a regional observation acquired at different wavelengths, it is possible to arrive at different cloud cover estimates (Koren et al., 2007).

The use of satellite instruments allow the study of cloud properties along great areas, allowing for a large-scale analysis that would be impossible with in situ measurements. However, for the evaluation of cloud fraction, it is necessary to consider the type and frequency of the measurement. Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) sensors aboard Terra and Aqua satellites allow cloud cover retrievals with 250 m spatial resolution on visible and near-infrared wavelengths, and several other wavelengths with resolution from 500 m to 1 km. However, these satellites fly over a given region of the globe only once in the daytime period, and one in the night time period. Regions close to the Equator may not be sampled every day. Geostationary satellites such as GOES can provide information every 30 minutes, with spatial resolution between 1 km and 4 km at visible, infrared and thermal wavelengths. The higher frequency of observation provided by geostationary satellites allows the investigation of the temporal evolution of the cloud cover; but its worst spatial resolution (compared to polar orbiting satellites) does not allow the detection of small-scale clouds, which are common on the Amazon at the beginning of convection processes.

Ground-based instruments have the geometric advantage, in relation to platforms aboard satellites, of being physically located closer to the analyzed cloud fields. This usually results in more accurate detections of cloud cover over a given location, but less representative on large scales. The detection of clouds from the surface can occur through passive measurements, such as radiometers, or active, with the use of radar or LIDAR systems. Each of these instruments uses a certain field of view (FOV). Shortwave radiometers perform measurements of incident radiation at the surface representing a hemispherical FOV of about 160°. Imaging cameras, such as the Total Sky Imager (TSI) can perform measurements with effective 100° FOV. In the case of active instruments such as radars and Lidars, the FOV may represent a narrow beam of 0.2° or less (Wu et al., 2014). In this case, cloud detection is done only on one column, and may differ substantially from larger FOV-based methods. The Figure, taken from Wu et al. (2014) shows a diagram illustrating the different observation geometries for detecting the fraction of cloud cover. These

differences necessarily result in divergences between the estimates of fraction of cloud cover over a given region.

An last but important problem is the fact that the CF platforms can have different retrieval durations and spatial resolutions. Normally, this difficulty is overcome by using common spatio-temporal averaging windows for the instruments being compared, however this approach requires the use of time interval and a spatial window for calculation the mean CF - and although there are some estimates for these parameters using theoretical approaches, there is no estimate by using empirical data.

In this work cloud fraction retrieved by different platforms are compared. To estimate the best-agreement resolution, averaging over different spatio-temporal windows were analysed. The influence of external key variables such as solar geometry and the seasonality was also investigated.

2. Methodology

2.1. Site description

Ground-based and satellite daytime retrievals of cloud fraction over Manacapuru, located at -3.2133°N , -60.5987°E , 36 m asl, in the Brazilian Amazon (Figure 2). During the GO Amazon experiment, from January 2014 to December 2015, (Martin et al., 2016) a suite of instruments to measure atmospheric and surface properties was operated by the Atmospheric Radiation

Measurement (ARM) Climate Research Facility of the United States Department of Energy (Martin et al., 2016) at this site. The study site is located about 70 km downwind of Manaus, where meandering winds alternate between clean and polluted atmospheric conditions, as the urban pollution plume intercepts the site (Martin et al., 2016).

Figure 2 - Location of the study site, near the city of Manaus in the Brazilian Amazon. The yellow box has a side length of 2.0° (~ 200 km). Basemap from Google Maps.

Daytime ground-based and satellite retrievals of cloud fraction in Manacapuru were compared. The data sets used in this study were obtained from surface radiometers, a Total Sky Imager, polar orbiting (MODIS) and geostationary satellites (GOES-13) and are described below in further detail.

2.2. Instrument platforms

2.2.1. ARM Total Sky Imager (TSI)

The TSI instrument provides daytime fractional cloud cover for solar zenith angles below 80° . The instrument acquires 352×288 pixel 24-bit color hemispherical sky images with a typical sampling rate of one image every 30

seconds¹. An image-processing algorithm analyzes the pixel color ratio to estimate the fractional cloud cover (Kassianov et al., 2005). The full ARM cloud cover dataset at T3 was used in this study, with a time span from December 23, 2013 to November 30, 2015.

2.2.2. ARM Radiative Flux Analysis (RFA)

The RFA is an ARM Value Added Product, i.e., a processed dataset combining measurements, algorithms and modeling. In this work, radiative fluxes measured at the T3 site by a surface broadband radiometer, for solar zenith angles below 80°, were processed to derive fractional cloud cover for both short (Long et al., 2006) and long (Long & Turner, 2008) wavelength ranges². The acquisition rate for the measurements was typically one retrieval per minute. Additionally, another two versions of the retrieval algorithms by Xie & Liu (2013) were applied to the measured shortwave radiative fluxes, to derive the fractional cloud cover: the original Xie & Liu procedure, and a second version including statistical corrections accounting for the radiation absorption effect by clouds. Hence in this study we used the full T3 ARM RFA cloud cover datasets for shortwave, longwave, Xie & Liu (2013) original algorithm, and Xie & Liu (2013) corrected algorithm. All of these datasets spanned the timeframe from December 23, 2013 to November 30, 2015.

2.2.3. NASA MODIS Terra and Aqua

MODIS is a multispectral sensor on board Terra (10h30 and 22h30 LT nominal overpass time) and Aqua (13h30 and 01h00 LT) satellites with nominal altitude of 705 km, on polar orbits that can assess the T3 site region once daily during daytime. In this work we considered a 2° box centered on the study site (cf. Fig. 2), to derive the daytime cloud fraction from MODIS cloud products MOD06_L2 (Terra) and MYD06_L2 (Aqua), originally presented at 5 km spatial resolution. A full description of the cloud product processing algorithm is given by Platnick et al. (2017) and Ackerman et al. (2010). The MODIS Terra and Aqua cloud fraction datasets used in this study corresponded to the time span from December 01, 2013 to February 01, 2016.

2.2.4. NOAA GOES-13 imager

GOES-13 was a NOAA operated geostationary satellite with nominal orbit of 35,800 km altitude, decommissioned on January 2018. The imager sensor acquired data under varying schedules determined by NOAA, with typical retrievals over the Amazon region every 30 minutes. In this work we used data from GOES-13 imager channels 1 and 4, centered around wavelengths 0.65 μm (1 km spatial resolution), and 10.7 μm (4 km resolution), respectively (Wylie et al., 2002). Raw count data was converted to reflectance units (channel 1) and brightness temperature (channel 4) following NOAA procedure recommendations³. Cloud fraction was assessed as the percentage of cloudy

¹ https://www.arm.gov/publications/tech_reports/handbooks/tsi_handbook.pdf (accessed May 24, 2018).

² <https://www.arm.gov/capabilities/vaps/radfluxanal> (accessed May 24, 2018).

³ <http://www.ospo.noaa.gov/Operations/GOES/calibration> (accessed May 24, 2018).

pixels in a grid box of variable side length, from 0.1° to 2.0° with 0.1° steps, centered at the T3 site (Fig. 2). Pixels were considered cloudy if their visible reflectance was above 0.125 and their brightness temperature was below 280 K. These empirical threshold values are adequate for the detection of clouds in the Amazon region, and over the T3 site specifically, where the surface is dominated by dark pixels over forests and rivers. There are also bright and hot pixels associated with high-sediment rivers, roads and urban areas that are discriminated by the empirical threshold values above. The cloud fraction dataset from GOES-13 used in this study spanned the timeframe from December 01, 2013 to December 01, 2015.

2.3 Resampling spatio-temporal windows

In order to compare instruments with different sampling rates and spatial resolutions, it was necessary to resample the datasets to generate data points with equivalent spatial and temporal resolutions. Resampling, in essence, consists of obtaining the average of the data within a defined window. In the context of this work, windows can be temporal, when comparing two surface instruments, or spatio-temporal, when a surface instrument is compared to a spaceborne one.

In a temporal window, the data is resampled within a defined time interval and the result is assigned to the midpoint of that interval. This midpoint can correspond to a specific reference, such as the overpass time of a satellite instrument. An illustration of the procedure is shown in Figure 3, showing the resampling process based on a reference platform, and resampling without a specific reference, both of which will be used later in this work.

Figure 3 - Illustration of the resampling procedure. The red and yellow boxes represents an resampling interval of 30min using platforms A and B

measurements, while the purple triangle represents an 1h interval resampling of the platform B measurements centered on the reference platform.

The spatio-temporal resampling is performed over the spatial coordinates of a box centered on the T3 site, in addition to the temporal resampling. Thus, for a spatio-temporal window one has two choices of parameters associated to the resampling procedure: the time interval and the spatial box size. Time intervals in this work ranged from 15 to 360 minutes. Box side lengths for the spatial resampling ranged from 0.1° to 2.0°, in 0.1° steps.

3. Results

3.1. Overview

The correlation between daytime cloud cover and cloud fraction datasets over the study site was initially examined⁴ considering a temporal window of 7 days and a spatial box side length of 1°. This spatio-temporal scale captures large scale variations in the occurrence of clouds, and serves as a baseline benchmark to understand how the different platforms fare. For this particular spatio-temporal window, Figure 4 shows the correlation between the time series of cloud cover and cloud fraction obtained from the several instruments used in this study. The ARM RFA cloud cover dataset (Long et al., 2006; Long & Turner, 2008) for shortwave (longwave) wavelengths is denoted as Long SW (Long LW). The ARM RFA cloud cover datasets processed under the Xie & Liu (2013) algorithms with and without a correction for cloud radiation absorption were also included in the analysis.

Figure 4 shows that the correlations in general are above 0.80 - with some notable exceptions, such as the cloud cover comparisons between Long LW vs. TSI, and Xie & Liu vs. TSI. These are remarkable since both instruments are operated on the surface and represent similar FOVs. These comparisons highlight how the interpretation of measured physical data (ARM RFA measurements), by applying a specific algorithm such as Long & Turner (2008) or Xie & Liu (2013), influences the final result for cloud cover estimates. It also illustrates the complexity of comparing cloud cover and cloud fraction estimated by different platforms.

Note that the cloud albedo correction in the Xie & Liu (2013) algorithm - indicated in Figure 4 as "Xie & Liu corrected" - represents a negligible difference in the resulting correlation with the other platforms, when compared to the uncorrected algorithm ("Xie & Liu" in the figure).

⁴ A repository with all comparisons described in this work is available at: <http://fap.if.usp.br/~danlessa/results/resultado-ic>.

3.2. Spatio-temporal window analysis

The specific spatio-temporal window used in the previous section, selecting a 1° area box and 7 days of data, allowed understanding how different platforms are expected to correlate on a large scale. However there is no guarantee that it represents an optimized choice. In this section this problem is attacked directly by studying how variations in the size and temporal scope of the spatio-temporal window impact over the correlations found. The resampling time is varied from 15 to 360 minutes with 15 min increments, while the size of the resampling area box is varied from 0.1° to 2.0°, in steps of 0.1°. For each combination, we calculate the number of data points used in each dataset, the Pearson correlation index between them, and the corresponding p-value to assess the resulting statistical significance. For the sake of simplicity, the only p-values shown in the figures below correspond to the worst possible (least significant) comparative case. In these analyses this corresponds to the box of smaller spatial size and shorter time interval, which resulted in the smallest sample size and highest p-value.

Figure 5 shows examples derived by applying this methodology to three pairs of instruments (Figs. 5a to 5c). Each matrix element in Figure 5 shows the

correlation coefficient between two specified datasets, for the spatio-temporal window defined by axes coordinates. Figure 5a shows that when considering TSI and GOES-13, the best correlation is found when using 30-105 min of TSI data centered around GOES-13 acquisition times, to compare with GOES-13 data in spatial boxes of 0.1-0.3 degree side length, centered at the TSI instrument location. In Figure 5b one notices the best correlation between the shortwave radiometer data (Long SW) and GOES-13 is obtained with spatial boxes of about 0.2 degrees (similar to Figure 5a), but with a much shorter temporal window of 15-30 min. Comparing two satellite cloud fraction retrievals in Figure 5c, between MODIS/Terra (1 daytime retrieval per day) and GOES-13 (~20 daytime retrievals per day), one notices the best correlation is defined by large scale variations: a spatial box of 0.5-0.9 degrees around the T3 site, and a temporal window of 300-360 min of GOES-13 data, around the MODIS/Terra overpass time, which essentially represents the full daytime GOES-13 data series at any given day with a MODIS/Terra retrieval. Notice, however, that Figure 5c shows the correlation coefficient varies slowly with the size of the temporal window, changing from the maximum of 0.79 to a value of about 0.76 if the temporal window is reduced from 360 min to 120 min. Comparing the results from Figures 5a to 5c it is clear the optimal correlation between any given instrument pair is strongly contingent to the platforms. It is not possible to anticipate the best spatio-temporal window from instruments characteristics, their position relative to the surface, or sampling rate, hence the need for the calculations performed here.

Next we examine the influence of solar illumination geometry on the correlation coefficient obtained when comparing cloud cover and cloud fraction series derived from given instrument pairs.

Figure 5 - Correlation distribution between cloud cover and cloud fraction from different platforms, for the spatio-temporal windows indicated in the axes. Isolines of constant correlation, in steps of 0.02, are shown to highlight local maxima. a) TSI vs. GOES-13, least significant comparison p-value (p): $<10^{-32}$, number of samples (N): 13030; b) Long SW vs. GOES-13, $p < 10^{-32}$, N: 13180; c) MODIS/Terra vs. GOES-13, $p = 5 \times 10^{-32}$, N: 191.

3.3. Solar geometry

The lifetime of convective clouds in the Amazon Basin is strongly controlled by the daily cycle of surface heating and humidity fluxes. The development of the boundary layer and the occurrence of convective clouds is thus associated to the solar illumination geometry, or the time of the day for these phenomena. In this section we analyze correlations between different instruments, for selected time intervals of up to 3 hours.

Figure 6 shows spatio-temporal correlation maps between GOES-13 cloud fraction and TSI cloud cover datasets, for the time windows 15-18h UTC (11-14h LT, Figure 6a) and 18-21h UTC (14-17h LT, Figure 6b). The marked differences between results in Figures 6a and 6b highlight the dynamic nature of cloud formation and development, as seen by surface and spaceborne instruments. The data acquired around local noon (Figure 6a) correspond to developing clouds, while in the afternoon (Figure 6b) one usually has mature cloud systems at the peak of daily convective activity. The optimal spatio-temporal window when analyzing data around local noon (Figure 6a) indicates large scale variations drive the correlation between the datasets. On the other hand, Figure 6b shows a clear correlation maximum when considering 135 min of TSI cloud cover data, compared to GOES-13 cloud fraction derived over a 0.3 deg side length box.

In Figure 7 the spatio-temporal correlation maps between the GOES-13 cloud fraction and the ARM RFA Long SW cloud cover data series are shown for time windows of 15-18h UTC (Figure 7a) and 18-21h UTC (Figure 7b). In both cases the correlations vary relatively slowly close to the maximum of about 210 min and a 0.3-0.4 deg side length box. However, in absolute values the correlations around local noon (Figure 7a) are about 22% greater than in the afternoon (Figure 7b).

The contrasting results observed in Figures 6 and 7 emphasize the importance of precisely defining the methodology for comparing correlations of cloud cover and/or cloud fraction series between instruments. For a specific pair of instruments the time of day can be decisive when defining an optimal spatio-temporal window for the analysis (e.g. Figure 6), while for others it can represent a significant impact on the value of the max expected correlation (e.g. Figure 7).

Figure 7 - Correlation distribution between GOES-13 cloud fraction and ARM RFA Long SW cloud cover data sets a) from 15h to 18h UTC; b) from 18h to 21h UTC. Isolines of constant correlation as in Figure 5.

The examples shown in Figures 6 and 7 were based on a 3h long time window. These analyses can be carried out with time windows of varying duration. Considering that each time interval duration can result in different maximum correlations, Figure 8 shows an example that summarizes possible outcomes when comparing GOES-13 and TSI data series. The correlations found in Figure 8 are relatively high (above 0.84) for most of the combinations, indicating little sensitivity to the time window duration. Analyzing the results in Figure 8 one can determine heuristically the optimal time window duration, for a given starting time, in the comparison of the two data series. For instance, when investigating the onset of convection in the Amazon, one usually seeks to analyze cloud properties at the beginning of the day, e.g. 12UTC (08 LT). From Figure 8 in this case the best correlations are obtained with a window duration of 1 to 3 hours. More generally, from 12-14 UTC (08-10LT) the shorter the time window the better the correlation. Then, from ~15-17UTC (11-13 LT) there is a reversal in trend when the longer the time window the better the correlation. Finally, when convection is in a mature state in the afternoon, from 18-20UTC (14-16LT), again shorter time windows result in better correlations. Physically one could expect different patterns when comparing cloud datasets, since the average daytime Amazon convection process can be composed of onset, transition, and mature stages corresponding to the morning, noon, and afternoon timeframes.

Table 2 - Recommendations of temporal and spatial windows to be adopted when comparing the indicated instruments in order to maximize the correlation of CF in Manacapuru (AM). The range of correlations obtained by adopting the windows as well as the time intervals of the data in the observations, if applicable, is also set.

Platform pair	Optimal temporal window	Optimal spatial window	Optimal time interval	Expected correlation
TSI and Long SW	Agnostic	N/A	12h to 20h UTC	0.91 to 0.96
TSI and GOES	1h to 3h	Between 0.2 and 0.5 degrees	12h to 20h UTC	0.83 to 0.88
TSI and MODIS	15min to 90min	Between 0.1 and 0.2 degrees	N/A (one point per day)	0.81 to 0.86
Long SW and GOES	Larger than 1h	Between 0.4 and 0.6 degrees	14h to 20h UTC	0.87 to 0.90
Long SW and MODIS	2h to 4h	Between 0.2 and 0.3 degrees	N/A (one point per day)	0.83 to 0.86
GOES and MODIS	N/A	N/A	N/A (one point per day)	0.78 to 0.87

Maximum correlation maps similar to the example in Figure 8 were calculated for all instrument pairs considered in this work. Inspecting these results and considering the optimal spatio-temporal windows exemplified in Figure 5, one can derive a set of recommended comparison parameters, summarized in Table 2. For a given instrument pair, Table 2 shows a recommendation for the duration of the temporal window and the size of the spatial window when comparing datasets of cloud fraction and/or cloud cover. It also shows the recommended subset of daytime hours, related to the solar illumination geometry. The recommendations in Table 2 do not take into account the dynamics of cloud lifetime evolution during daytime. For instance, when seeking to analyze the onset of convection one should further restrict the datasets to morning hours, besides the spatio-temporal considerations listed in Table 2. [add here a specific example from Table2]

3.4 Seasonal analysis

Seasonal variations influence the formation, evolution, and the vertical and horizontal distribution of clouds in the Amazon. For cloud cover and/or fraction assessments instrument performance can, in principle, depend on season by means of the skill needed to distinguish cloudy from clear sky scenes. Considering the average monthly rainfall in the Manaus region (REF), the dry season corresponds to the months between June and November, while the wet season runs from December to May.

Correlation distributions between instrument pairs were examined for wet and dry seasons. Figure 9 shows an example for the correlations of cloud fraction

from GOES-13 and cloud cover from TSI, for dry and wet seasons. During the wet season (Figure 9a) the correlations are stronger than during the dry season (Figure 9b). The optimal spatio-temporal window in the wet season (Figure 9a) corresponds to 60 min averages in the TSI data series, to be compared to 0.2 degree side length boxes of GOES-13 cloud fraction around the sampling site. The dry season shows a similar result, although with smaller correlation values. The isolines of constant correlation have a similar distribution for wet and dry seasons.

So for this section, additional correlation distributions for all time intervals are generated for both the wet and dry seasons.

When adopting the recommendations at Table 2, the following non-trivial results can be cited, which are illustrated by Figure 9 and 10:

- The correlation between the all instruments in relation to MODIS Terra and Aqua is better in the dry season than in the wet season, with an improvement of about 32%.
- The correlation between GOES and TSI is best in the wet season by about 8% in relation to the dry season.

Finally, it must be established that there is a difference in the absolute value of the maximum correlations, when using the Table 2 parameters on the wet/dry seasons. These differences are summarized by Table 3.

Figure 10 - Correlation distribution between the TSI and GOES CFs on the wet season (a) and dry season (b)

Table 3 - Maximum correlation on each season when Table 2 recommendations are adopted

Platforms	Maximum correlation on the wet season	Maximum correlation on the dry season
TSI and Long	0.96	0.96
TSI and GOES	0.89	0.83
TSI and MODIS	0.78 (Terra) / 0.77 (Aqua)	0.85 (Terra) / 0.82 (Aqua)

Long and GOES	0.88	0.90
Long and MODIS	0.69 (Terra) / 0.70 (Aqua)	0.81 (Terra) / 0.82 (Aqua)
GOES and MODIS	0.63 to 0.71 (Terra) / 0.61 to 0.82 (Aqua)	0.67 (Terra) / 0.71 (Aqua)

4. Conclusions

As indicated by Figures 4-9, the correlation of the CF values obtained between different platforms can vary substantially throughout the day or according to the use of the temporal and spatial windows used in the calculations. Therefore, it is proposed to avoid the use of general rules for the comparison between CFs. An example is given by the contrast between Figures 5 and 7, in which the correlations can be 0.66 if the used data are relative for the whole day or 0.88 if a optimal spatio-temporal window is adopted.

But if an general rule is needed, there are indications that there are ideal sizes of space-time windows to be adopted when comparing CFs measurements between different platforms. Specifically, Table 2 contains recommendations for optimal spatio-temporal windows, ideal time intervals and expected correlations.

It is also recommended that future comparative or descriptive publications on CFs show results broken down at certain time intervals throughout the day instead of averaging over all day.

As an commentary on the results of Table 2, it is noted that the results are in agreement with the work elaborated by Sena et al. (2016) in which it was found that the clouds present in the atmospheric column are thermodynamically connected to the surface and the planetary boundary layer in the middle of the day and disconnected at the beginning and end of the day. These findings are in agreement with the fact described in this work that the exclusion of data at the beginning and end of the day allow the maximization of correlations between some pairs of platforms.

Lastly, we found that the season can have an impact on the correlation between the platforms CF values as show by Table 3.

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Appendix

Comparison procedures

With the resampling on space-time windows being defined, the following procedure is adopted as a methodological basis for the generation of a data product that allow comparison between two platforms:

Procedure when at least one platform is satellite-based.

1. An spatial box size and an time interval is defined
2. The points of the platform with lowest retrieval frequency are defined as references for resampling
3. The reference CF values are averaged (if applicable) based on the spatial box size centered on Manacapuru site
4. For every reference point, the CF values on the compared platform is averaged based on the spatial box size (if applicable) centered on Manacapuru site and on the time interval around the reference
5. A new tabular file is generated where every row represents a datapoint which contains the resampled CF for the reference and compared platforms.

Procedure when both platforms are soil-based.

1. An time interval is defined
2. Both platforms CF values are averaged around the time interval and using the averaged timestamp as datapoint time
3. A new tabular file is generated where every row represents a point which contains the resampled CF for both platforms on the average time.

Using the products resulting from these procedures, we are then in a position to generate pairwise comparison metrics for the platforms. For this research, the metric to be used is the Pearson correlation coefficient.

Acronyms of the compared platforms

- TSI - CF acquired from the GOAmazon's Total Sky Imager
- GOES-13 - CF acquired from GOES-13 using channels 1 and 4
- Xie & Liu - CF acquired from GOAmazon's Radiative Flux Analyzer using a algorithm described by Xie & Liu et al
- Xie & Liu corrected - Same as above, but with an correction for cloud albedo
- Long SW and LW - CF acquired from GOAmazon's Radiative Flux Analyzer using a algorithm described by Long et al using shortwave and longwave radiative fluxes.

- MODIS Terra and Aqua